

Maturing in Practice: EdTech Innovation Processes in Dutch Higher Education

Version: Beta

Acceleration plan
Educational innovation
with ICT

Maturing in Practice: EdTech Innovation Processes in Dutch Higher Education
Supporting the EdTech innovation process in higher education

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Educational innovation with ICT

Working Group EdTech for Educational Innovation

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Purpose: This report exists as the groundwork or rationale for the Innovation Processes maturity model. Within this report, a reader can better understand the connections between dimensions, what the definition for the dimensions are and what indicators are connected to the various levels of maturity. Important considerations for the context surrounding the model and rationale for its development are also discussed.

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1. Introducing a Model

Making a landscape of various organizational characteristics more relatable is easier with maturity models. These models can help see a more objective performance assessment and or indications of how possible new levels of readiness or development can help lead to better performance overall.

To find an effective way of examining institutional preparedness and maturity of innovation processes regarding educational technologies, or EdTech, the Working Group EdTech for Educational Innovation has facilitated the creation of a maturity model with its community. The target audience for this model is Dutch Higher Education institutions, but EdTech vendors may also benefit from knowing the indicators and different dimensions found in this model. Higher education institutions in the Netherlands are considered to benefit most when preparing their organization on various dimensions of this model.

This model stands as a second piece to the continuing compendium of following publications in the project *Supporting the EdTech innovation process in higher education* being developed by the EdTech work group. The publications to follow will build on the audience and research collected during this model overview report to produce a general maturity model for EdTech innovation in Dutch universities. This work group's previous report, *Avontuurlijke samenwerkingen: EdTech modellen van experimenten tot toepassing (2022)*, reviewed several educational institutions in the Netherlands and the way in which they procure and innovate with educational technologies. That report opened up conversations on how to better understand the connections of various departments, stakeholders, and broader aspects of innovation processes. Connections aside, there is still a need to shape conversations regarding how Dutch Higher Education might position itself for future capabilities in EdTech innovation. **In other words, the maturity model proposed in this report presents current descriptions of real EdTech innovation processes and recognizes the potential advancement of each dimension.**

Motivated by the need for both more awareness of EdTech innovations and the goals surrounding this work group, the maturity model stands as a conversation starter mainly for higher education institutions. **The model enables both EdTech early adopters and more mature institutions to recognize how various organizational dimensions are related in shaping innovation processes.** This relation is applicable to both the mindsets regarding innovation in organizations as well as the actual processes needed to produce innovative outcomes. The goal of this model then, is **not** to suggest that all institutions should be at the 'most mature' level of all dimensions. **Instead, this maturity model supports organi-**

zations and their members to find ways to meet strategic, visionary, and forward-thinking goals together if those goals are related to innovative practices and processes in educational technology development.

During the summer of 2022 the workgroup will create more supplemental materials to support institutions who want to increase their maturity level on specific elements of the model. These instruments will ensure that the maturity model proposed in this report can be read and applied with less friction and interpretation. These instruments will be found on the Versnellingsplan website and will be free to use for anyone. Ultimately, the projects found in the *Versterken van het EdTech innovatieproces in het hoger onderwijs Werkgroep EdTech voor onderwijsinnovatie* portfolio are developed to begin raising awareness about EdTech in Dutch Higher education institutions.

2. Considerations for this Model

The EdTech work group created this unique project to stimulate organizations and capable stakeholders to be creative with their thinking. For instance, inspiring them to consider what EdTech within and around their institutions are influencing or maturing towards. Or, to be able to grasp the complexities of EdTech innovation in their entire organization. Additionally, this project asks for these same people to recognize their own level of maturity, requiring reflection and focus to make clear what they are capable of right now in this domain of innovation.

Some key considerations were taken during the development of this model. The following is a list of some of these contextual considerations.

- **Responsibility:** This model was designed with a 'scope of change' in mind. Universities and higher education organizations in the Netherlands have a variety of duties and responsibilities they owe to their members, but in turn can also steer a large amount of change in communities tied to their institutions. The maturity model proposed in this report tries to stay within a reasonable frame of responsibility regarding the dimensions described. In other words, the dimensions and expectations in this maturity model are focused on what is possible for universities to reasonably change or influence.
- **Inclusion is not enough:** To create a more active and applied maturity model, the Werkgroep EdTech prioritized moving beyond simply 'including' new communities or stakeholders and instead activating or supporting new initiatives. Talking about or becoming aware of the need for new processes or communities is instead considered part of the first steps in innovation for EdTech.
- **Awareness:** The use of Maslow's phases of assimilating new knowledge, skills and competences was used as a kind of sub-layer to the levels of maturity. Maslow's language fits neatly into the expected competencies and awareness-raising aspects of innovations in EdTech. These behavior describing phases also raise new questions about what kind of EdTech we want to begin developing for the future and how through this language we can communicate current institutional feasibility for innovation now.
- **Compiling dimensions:** The four main dimensions in this model are comprised of a condensed version of dimensions found in the famous 7-S model by McKinsey. Strategy has been combined with vision and management style, Structure with processes, People

with culture and behaviors, and Systems. With this, the model adopts a much larger variety of processes, people and tools, yet is not too vague. The model is designed to stay within the unique scope of EdTech for higher education.

3. Dimension Definitions

People

This dimension is a combination of the skills, staff roles, and styles or ways of working in the organization. The People dimension holds a lot of characteristics that are difficult to measure or grapple with. Culture, behavior, community, competencies, and leadership are all considered tied to the People dimension. People as a dimension will share a lot of overlap with the other dimensions, but especially strategy and structure; where strategy needs to be developed with sub-dimensions like ‘leadership’ and ‘community’.

Structure

Structure as a dimension includes the processes in consideration for innovation. This could be procurement, agility of changing processes, or even exit strategies for tools and applications. Connections exist as well in this model to Structure. Processes as a sub-dimension will need to develop with People in mind. This requires looking to other sub-dimensions for help and seeing connections between them, for instance ‘decision making’ in Strategy will demand processes to be created with people in mind and the right processes in place to facilitate those decisions.

Strategy

The dimension called Strategy holds different hard elements of policies, strategy, steering and budgeting. These are elements that are agreed on by the organization as necessary for the future of the organization and to steer it towards improvements and through change. Other subdimensions include decision-making, responsibility, and ownership. Strategy will rely on other dimensions to produce effective and valued visions, steering, etc. For instance, without the involvement of a sub-dimension like ‘community’, a policy may be created that doesn’t represent its beneficiaries’ interests.

Systems

A Systems dimension entails many elements, including interoperability of software systems, experimentation environments, and standardization in architecture. Other Systems sub-dimensions include an inventory of all applications in use or procured, security and privacy systems, and data management. While the dimension Systems are based on very tangible elements, there still exists a reliance and connections to other (sub)dimensions. One example is of an institution that has obtained a clear data management system (or EdTech inventory system), but no processes have been developed to take advantage of such systems. Naturally, this leads to discussions with communities and leadership roles to create clear, accessible language for processes for the Systems necessary to innovate further.

4. Maturity Level Descriptions

Level 1 (least mature)

There is no awareness of or sharing knowledge about EdTech tools or innovation processes for it. There is no experimentation or support for experimentation amongst any departments with EdTech tools. Generally, people will not have the competencies to effectively experiment with EdTech. Furthermore, no EdTech focused community exists within the institution. Institutions are often unaware of their own ignorance regarding EdTech innovations and tooling at this level. A willingness to learn more about the added value of EdTech innovations is necessary at this level.

Level 2

EdTech tools and innovations begin to be talked about within departments. These ideas for new EdTech tools are not discouraged by those who will support the tooling on a technical level, there may even be new procurement processes available for new EdTech. Interest begins to build around having an EdTech focused community, but there are still no connections made to strategic university goals to steer or support the EdTech community. At this level, institutions often become aware of their ignorance and are not sure where to start with EdTech and innovative processes. Institutions at this level may begin to have developed processes for how to safely experiment with EdTech at this level as well as inventory what tools are used in the institution.

Level 3

People have begun to experiment together across different departments with various processes related to EdTech. In this level, universities may actively be organizing events for EdTech and encouraging growth of the community. Knowledge sharing between various roles is not connected to one strategy nor one vision, but these plans may be being outlined at the policy level. Now with more converging dimensions, the needs of different education programs and departments should be in assessment. This assessment is in part catalyzed by a now standardized architecture to build on for both EdTech vendors and internal creators or applications.

Level 4

EdTech is found throughout the institution in various forms, both in and outside of classroom settings. People are incentivized to experiment and have clear goals on how didactical and pedagogical concerns connect to tooling. Moreover, people are trained with digital literacy in mind so that any EdTech tools that are experimented with are accessible and applied continually. Processes have been agreed on regarding testing, experimenting with

and implementing EdTech tools across departments. Employees in instructional roles expect to be able to locate information about how to implement and experiment with new EdTech tools that they believe are connected to didactical practices. There is now a fully interoperable EdTech portfolio, or inventory that does not solely rely on a learning management system for usage. A function is created to focus solely on EdTech innovations and future thinking of these tools.

5. Model Walkthrough

Goal of this section: To enable a reader to be able to understand and apply the maturity model to their organization or department.

Walking through a model is like peeling an onion, there are many layers, but they all wrap around a similar core. Managing the different layers of this model requires consideration from many departments; a multi-disciplinary approach which is also often found in EdTech implementation.

Example frame for People dimension and questions

The model is developed around four dimensions: People, Structure, Strategy and Systems.

1. Start by understanding each dimension from the previous section of this descriptive report.
 - Make note of who you may need to ask questions to regarding each sub-dimension of each dimension.
 - Each dimension should be considered in later maturities, connected to other dimensions.
2. Look at the People dimension.
 - The first sub-dimension is Culture.
 - The current version has 3 characteristics of the sub-dimension, and one question for each characteristic.
 - Answer each question with either a yes or no answer.

- Tally up how many 'yes's you have answered and look to the next sub-dimension that has questions, like community.
- Continue this process until you have completed all sub-dimension questions in each characteristic.

3. Add all yes's together and look towards the level indicators above the dimensions.

- Each level should have an action that is being completed or should be started in your organization to be the most effective with EdTech.

There are likely many ways of using this model. Please feel free to share how you took advantage of this model to the EdTech Work group!

Entering a new phase

Moving forward from spring 2022, the EdTech work group would like to test this model. To use this model and reveal its strengths and weaknesses would allow not only critical feedback, but real use cases for its effectiveness. The EdTech work group plans to revisit this model in the fall of 2022, where new (sub)dimensions may be added, reworked, or cut. Level indicators will need to be more clearly defined, and the EdTech communities' feedback will be required. Grasping the sheer complexity of multidisciplinary workings amongst departments in higher education requires a map. The map should display a landscape of both a network of stakeholders as well as the steps or paths necessary to move between levels across the (education) scene. This model is the first drawing of that map and this work group hopes to have enabled any institution interested in EdTech innovation to take their first steps onto this complex and increasingly populated landscape.

References

Volwassenenleren.nl. "Maslow: (On)Bewust (on)Bekwaam." Accessed May 13, 2022. volwassenenleren.nl/maslow-onbewust-onbekwaam.

MindTools. "The McKinsey 7-S Framework: - Making Every Part of Your Organization Work in Harmony." Accessed May 13, 2022. www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newSTR_91.htm.

Van Valkenburg, Willem, Wiebe Dijkstra, Bea de los Arcos, and Katie Goeman. "European Maturity Model for Blended Education," 2020.

Verdonck Klooster and Associates. "Data-gedreven Werken." *Data & AI* (blog), n.d. www.vka.nl/product/datagedreven-werken.

The Acceleration Plan for Educational Innovation with IT is a four-year programme of the Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences, the Universities of the Netherlands and SURF. The aim of the programme is to bring together initiatives, knowledge, and experiences and to quickly and concretely get started with opportunities for higher education. This is done in eight zones and three working groups. The working group EdTech for educational innovation aims to support higher education in the Netherlands with Educational Technology.

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